

Education: Then vs Now

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Abstract: Education is one of the major components in human's life. Education helps in learning all the fundamentals which are very essential for the humans to survive and progress in his life. A man without education is like a tree which bears no fruits. So, education is vital in order to fulfil the purpose of every human being in this world. Education brings out the person's interest in any particular field in which he can put his maximum efforts and excel with beautiful colours. Education enlightens the power of knowledge and wisdom. In order to get in-depth knowledge in a particular concept there are introduction of various tools which helps you to uncover all your doubts. Though these digital tools are occupying a major part in the field of education but they should be used wisely in order to get the maximum benefits out of it.

Keywords: *Learning, Assessment, Digital learning, Educational tools, Technology era.*

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Introduction

Education in different forms has been in existence since time immemorial of global civilization where the transfer of knowledge and skills takes place across the generations. The emergence of writing was the first fundamental step in designing of teaching tool. The earliest teaching tools were found to be ancient scripts written on bamboo leaves. In ancient times there was the use of various teaching aids in which the notable one is the erasable tablet used by a Roman Educator Quintilian. The tablet (Buck GH, 1989) was constructed with wax-like material and written using a wood or metal stylus. In this modern era, we use pencils, pen, paper for writing but before the arrival of these inventions stylus and stone slates (Marvel, 2012) were used for writing. The overall progression of the student should be the ultimate goal of education, relating to the inspiring words of Mahatma Gandhi - Father of our nation, "By education, I mean an all-round drawing out of the best in child and body, mind and spirit". In today's scenario, global wealth has been shifted towards knowledge and skills rather than physical assets (Colin N, 2000). The quality of teaching is one of the crucial factors for the academic success (Darling-Hammond L, 2009) of the students endorsed by various academic institutions. To make the teachers stay updated and engaged in their fields a huge amount of money is spent on conducting various faculty development programs (FDP), thereby the overall quality of teaching can be improved.

Key differences between 20th century and 21st education:

The education in 20th century involves

- Time-based
- Textbook-driven

- Passive learning
- Fragmented learning
- Teacher is the only judge.

20th century education provided a teacher-centred classroom with a differentiated curriculum and students will work autonomously to understand the information. The teacher functioned as the "Guru", the contributor of all skills and knowledge (20th century vs 21st century model of education, 2016). In the 20th century, the major role played as a teaching aid were blackboards, OHP (Over Head Projector), PowerPoint presentations. The influence of technology was very minimal in the 20th - century.

The 21st century is considered to be the era of Technology-enhanced learning (TEL) research which emphasizes on various nascent technologies like Virtual Reality, cloud computing, Artificial Intelligence, Augmented Reality, Ubiquitous learning (u-learning), Mobile learning (M-learning) and learning analytics which provides new learning experiences to the students (Johnson L, 2014).

The education in the 21st century involves:

- Outcome-based
- Research-driven
- Active learning
- Integrated and interdisciplinary learning
- Self, peer and other assessments

21st - century skills are different from 20th - century skills primarily due to the arrival of very intricate information and communications technologies. Digital technology revolutionized communication and collaboration opportunities. 21st - century education provides a little freedom to the students which made the

classroom student-centred and helps them to achieve significant and team-oriented learning. The teachers have become a mentor providing better support, the catalyst for learning and lead the students to achieve their goals. Now students can work synergistically with their classmates and even with others across the globe through the advances in educational technology instead of sticking onto the one single book all time. There are various types of technology available for different skills like learning, assessment, writing, speaking, listening, presentation, etc., In today's fast changing digital world, online education has become an important role in assisting people to advance in their lives. Although the concept of online education dates back to the 1960s,

the first massive open online courses (MOOCs) arose only in 2008 (Bryant MG, 2017). The benefits of online courses over traditional education include the availability of individual training programmes, easy access to courses, and the opportunity to choose an educational path. Some of the MOOC providers includes Coursera, edX, Udacity, and futureLearn (Dhawk S, 2017). This review is aimed at focussing on the comparing education in 20th - century and 21st - century by the various educational tools employed at those times which gives an overview of the various changes that have occurred in the education. The transition of education tools is mentioned in Fig. 1.

Figure. 1 Transition of education tools

Education in 20th century

Chalkboards (Blackboards): The chalkboards are introduced for the purpose of providing information to a large group of audience at one time. The information displayed on the blackboard can be viewed by the students of the entire classroom. The use of blackboards emerged many years ago, in 1801, at Scotland, A large piece of slate was hung by a Geography teacher named James Pillans on the wall to take lecture to his students (history of the blackboard) George Baron, a mathematics teacher from the US used the slates connected together as a wall-mounted blackboard for the first time. In the US by the mid-19th century, every classroom was installed with a blackboard for lecturing students. However, the use of this blackboard by a teacher is based on their ability to sketch and inscribe on the board. It provided various opportunities for adding more creativities in their presentations of the content in various subjects. The blackboard is one of the brilliant innovations that became popular and well accepted by teachers around the world.

OHP'S (Over Head Projector): The OHP is a small machine that is specially designed to project an image or piece of information into the white screen or whiteboard. It can be used by lecturers in a similar way like the chalkboards. It also has an added advantage of the projector which helps the teachers to maintain the focus on students at all times rather than turning around always towards the board to write the important points. Similarly, these overhead projectors are very compact in nature when compared with any other visual aids such as charts or posters. The information provided can also be stored and reproduced at any time required. The room in which the projector is used need not to be darkened which allows the students to take notes without any hindrance. Using the overhead projectors does not require any technical skill by the person handling it, since the operation and handling of the overhead projectors are quite simple.

Google search on various tools for learning in education was investigated. Data were gathered from various sites. The key words used were "learning tools" "tools for learning," and "technology for learning", "learning tools of 21st century" "digital tools for learning" "top tools for learning". Out of the various results obtained the site which indicates the top tools for learning (toptools4learning) was selected. It includes the top list of 200 tools for learning in 2019 which was listed based on the 2,524 votes from 46 countries in the 13th annual learning tools survey, which was published on 18 September 2019.

From the list of top 200 tools, the first 25 tools were selected and categorized into 2 groups such as tools of 20th century, tools of 21st century based on the year of they were founded. Tools of 21st century were further subdivided into tools of early 2000 and newer tools. The timeline of various tools mentioned in Fig. 2.

Figure. 2 Timeline of various tools

Tools of 20th century

1. **MS-PowerPoint:** PowerPoint (Microsoft powerpoint) is an application to make presentations and display them as slideshows. PowerPoint allows the users to create and present their work much easily and also in a visually appealing way by using various smart art and animations provided. Using PowerPoint, you can add images, audio, video, etc., to your presentations which makes the presentation in such a way to grab the attention of the audience. It also has an interesting feature “presenter view” which enables the users to rehearse with their presentation by displaying the current slide they are presenting along with notes and the upcoming slide so that the presenter can stay focused and can connect better with audiences.
2. **MS-Word:** MS-word is an application using which users can create and edit the documents. MS-Word (Microsoft word) helps the users to write with more confidence by providing various suggestions like spelling, grammar, punctuations, etc.,. With the various tools available at fingertips, it allows the users to easily go from pen and paper to digital inking. It is one of the widely used application for various purposes starting from creating a project document, writing of a research paper, crafting of a perfect resume, etc.,.
3. **MS-Excel:** Ms-Excel (Microsoft excel) is an application used for creating spreadsheets from the available templates or based on the user’s choice. It is also used for performing calculations with modern formulas. It will learn patterns made by the user and organize the data entered thereby saving the user’s time. Charts and graphs in various designs can also be made by providing the data. The created Excel file can be shared across any devices.
4. **Google search:** Google search (How google search works) is an online search engine tool. Whenever the user searches it provides results with thousands/millions of webpages consisting of various helpful information. Before providing the result the Google itself organizes the information about webpages and provides the appropriate information required by the user. It is more like a library with unlimited information about various fields in it. Once the search has been started within a fraction of a second, Google’s Search algorithms will sort through hundreds of billions of webpages in the Search index to find out the most relevant and useful results. It helps the users to obtain the results quickly by providing the results in various formats like webpages, images, videos, news, navigations in the map, etc.,.
5. **Lynda.com: [linked in learning]:** Lynda.com (Linkedin about us) is one of the leading online learning platforms that helps the users to learn various fields like business, software, technology, marketing, creative skills, etc. and achieve their personal and professional goals. The users can be individuals, corporate, academic or government subscriptions, etc., have access to the E-learning platform. It provides users with a series of videos about top-quality courses that are taught by various reputed professionals from industries. For almost 20 years with more than 10,000 organizations, Lynda.com was helping students and professionals by providing various E-learning courses on different categories. It has added advantages of providing access to the courses with discounts for the students, business professionals and other organizations.
6. **Adobe Reader:** Adobe reader is PDF (Portable Document Format) viewing and editing software. It is a freely accessible application through which the users can view, edit, print,

share the PDFs. The users can also easily fill and sign the forms digitally and share across any devices instantly. The biggest advantage with the reader is it is the only PDF viewer (What's new in Acrobat DC) that has the provision for opening and interacting with all types of PDF contents such as forms and multimedia. It is also connected to Adobe Document Cloud services which enable the users to work on the PDF across multiple devices. The users can share the files within the reader because of the access to various tools like SharePoint, one drive, Dropbox.

Tools of 21st century

Tools of Early 2000:

1. YouTube: YouTube (What is Youtube) is a platform for watching and sharing videos. It is available as a website and application through which users can explore millions of videos created and posted by people across the world. It has wide categories of videos in it. Students can make use of this to watch any concepts as animated explanations or pictorial representations which helps them to understand the concepts in a better way. Since we remember things, we watch through our eyes better than the things we hear so students will remember the concepts for a longer time. It also has the provision of creating our own channel, where users can upload their own videos regarding any stream which can be beneficial for the learners in that stream.
2. Skype: Skype is a communication application (About Skype) through which users can make video calling which is available across multiple platforms. Using skype users can make one-one calling or group call for business purposes. In the case of education, skype works as a medium for conducting online classes where students and teachers in any part of the world could connect each other with this application. So, it will help to connect the educators across the world and students even in remote areas can acquire the knowledge from the teachers. It is free to use applications and up to a group of 50 people can make a group call.
3. Twitter: Twitter (How to use social media) is a social media application that allows users to perform microblogging. The users can create their own accounts and make their posts and share with others which are called tweets. The tweets might include text, images, or links referring to a particular website. Similarly, like other social media Instagram, Facebook, etc., users can follow the people or organizations which relate to your academic interest. It is not an application just for entertainment it also has some benefits for the students where they can keep them updated about the latest tweets which are made by various organizations and people in powerful positions. The news being telecasted are also dependent upon these tweets.
4. WhatsApp: WhatsApp is one of the world's most popular text and voice messaging applications. WhatsApp (Jackie D, 2021) provides free service that lets users message one another continuously with the people across the globe without interruption using mobile or desktops. It also provides privacy features like user's end-to-end encryption. Groups can be created comprising of the members of the family, friends, students of a classroom, etc., with a maximum of up to 256

participants. It allows the exchange of information among the students in a classroom. The information can be of any format like audio lessons, PPT materials or documents such as Word, books, video explanations, etc.,

5. WordPress: WordPress (What is WordPress, 2022) is an online website creation tool that is available as open-source. It is a simpler tool using which users can create their own website or blog. With the help of WordPress users can create websites/blogs of their own interest and can also gain income by increasing the views of customers and it also provides a platform for creating blogs where students can gain writing skills and internet marketing skills. It is found that more than 35.2% of the websites found on the internet are powered by WordPress. WordPress can be used for creating Business websites, e-Commerce stores, Blogs, Portfolios, Social networks, Membership sites, etc.,
6. Facebook: Facebook is a free social networking platform (Wayan V, 2010) where the users upon registration can connect with the people across the globe. The users can share their photos, videos and send messages to their family members, friends, etc. so that they can keep in touch. It allows the users to stay connected with the people who have lost contact because of the physical boundaries. The interesting part is the platform is available in almost 37 languages. Apart from entertainment, Facebook is a forum for the development of interpersonal communication skills for students. These kinds of interpersonal skills should be encouraged especially from these kinds of digital platforms like Facebook. Facebook enables the student to learn ICT (Information and Communications Technology) skills and group collaboration without getting bored.
7. Slack: Slack (Rob W, 2019) is a communication tool, specially designed for workplace activities. The users can send messages, share files, or tools altogether at one single place. It allows the users to send instant messages along with many add-ins are available for other workplace tools. However, the add-ins are not mandatory to use slack since the main function of slack is to talk with the team members. It has two options for chatting such as group chat called channels and one to one chatting. In slack, the users create channels for office, team, projects, etc. and share the files through it. After creating channels users can make private conversations by making the file open only for a particular member or group conversations.
8. Articulate: Articulate (Software advice Articulate 360 software, 2021) is a cloud-based e-learning platform through which users can build their own online courses. It has many inbuilt features like templates for slides, colour themes, text editor, font, screen recording and software stimulation. The users can build their e-learning expertise by accessing the various training tools which are provided in the e-learning module. There are various e-learning modules available. The content library present comprises of various pictures, character, videos and templates which can be used for creating the online course. The users can design interactive courses that work across multiple devices using the authoring app that comes along with the application.

9. **Wikipedia:** Wikipedia is a multilingual, web-based, free-content encyclopaedia which is supported by the Wikimedia Foundation. The content displayed on Wikipedia (Adam C, 2013) is openly editable. The content is written by different volunteers who are skilled or interested in that particular area. The volunteers will not receive any pay for creating or editing the contents. However, to prevent disruption editing is restricted in some cases. The content created will be continuously updated by the volunteers which help to learn about the updated facts and events. Since many people collaboratively working to formulate and update the contents it makes Wikipedia more comprehensive than a regular encyclopaedia.
10. **Dropbox:** Dropbox is a cloud-based productivity tool which is designed for the users through which they can save and store their various files or documents in the cloud. The file saved in the cloud can be shared with others whenever required. The biggest advantage of dropbox (Afshan B) is its amazing storage capacity, sharing features and the backup facility where the files we store will not get lost/deleted permanently, in case of any system failures because the files can be retrieved back by using this feature. The other key features of Dropbox include multiple device accessibility, auto-updates, large file share ability, offline access, manual bandwidth setting, security, etc.,
11. **LinkedIn:** LinkedIn is a social network application which enables the users to develop their career and build their professional network. The users should create their own profiles comprising of all the academic and professional details including a resume. They can search for jobs, interact with various professionals across the country and thereby they can improve their professional reputation by posting about their various achievements. It is available as a free version and premium subscription version. With LinkedIn premium (Dave J, 2019) users will able to have additional benefits like access to various online courses, unlimited requesting option, etc... LinkedIn has become one of the best platforms providing employability services by posting about the various job openings in different organizations to the users irrespective of their fields in the best way. LinkedIn also opens the opportunity for the users to connect with various organizations and business professionals in their area which helps them to stay updated and build up their skills and knowledge.
12. **Feedly:** Feedly is a web-based, news-aggregation service. With the help of feedly (How to use feedly for tracking blogs) the users can read the contents of the blog in their mobile or desktop by adding the content which is present as RSS (Real Simple Syndication) available on any websites. It prevents frequent visiting of the users to the source site for checking any updates in the blog because every new update added to that blog can be seen in feedly itself.
13. **AnswerGarden:** AnswerGarden is a minimalistic feedback tool. It can be used in both classrooms and workplaces for conducting creative brainstorming sessions. The features of Answergarden (Russell Stannard, 2017) is used by the teachers to assess the student's level of knowledge on a particular topic. It is also used in conferences and even by

bloggers to poll their visitors. It comprises of various modes like classroom mode, brainstorm mode, locked mode and moderator mode. As a whole, it is an idea-generating website that stimulates the creative minds of students to bring out various ideas.

14. **Google forms:** Google forms is an online-based application which is used for creating forms for collecting data. Both students and teachers can use this for taking surveys or quizzes or registration forms for events. After completion of the form, it can be shared with the responders as a link, email as a message or by embedding into a web page. The data collected will be stored in a spreadsheet.

Tools of 21st century

NEWER TOOLS

1. **Microsoft teams:** Microsoft teams (7 Things you should know about Microsoft teams, 2021) is a chat-based collaboration tool that helps to connect with the teams who are present globally or remote and work together via a common space. It provides an option of one-to-one chatting, team chatting and collaboration of documents. The features provided will help the teams to work without having stress about switching over various applications to get the project completed. The workspace can be shared with numerous applications like Microsoft PowerPoint, Word, Excel, Planner, One note, etc. It also provides the timings of the scheduled meeting, subject and list of attending persons. Also, it provides a video interaction the team members using skype interaction which promotes engagement among team members.
2. **Wakelet:** Wakelet is a curation tool (Kathleen Morris, 2018), using which the users can organize, save and share the content which they found around the web. It will help the users to build their own collections. The collections can be of your own interest like images tweet, text, or PDF. The collection can be made by adding the link of the particular image or text. The collection made will enable users to create their own fictional story comprising of text and images.
3. **Loom:** Loom is a screen casting software. Using loom (Kathleen Morris, 2019), users can record the camera and screen along with the audio. The video can be recorded for a long time as long as you need it. The provisions provided for recording include users who can just record their face or screen or combination of both. After recording, it can be shared as a URL (Uniform Resource Locator) or MP4 file.
4. **Immersive reader:** Immersive reader (Vernoiica, 2018) is a tool that helps to enhance the reading and writing for the users regardless of their age and ability. Reading comprehension and fluency in English can be improvised by using this tool. It works in Microsoft application, specially designed for people with print disabilities like dyslexia, dysgraphia, vision impairment, etc. using assistive technologies. The various features include adjusting the text space, formatting the background colour, font size optimization, syllabification and highlighting of verbs, nouns, adjectives, etc.
5. **ScreenCastify:** ScreenCastify will record your screen which is available as Chrome Browser extension. Using this, users can record the entire screen activity with the webcam. It also

enables features of the laser pointer, erase, write, draw and time of recording. It records the screen along with the audio but sometimes, the sound can be hollow when the proper mic is not used. With the help of screencastify (Amy BL, 2021), students can gain public speaking skills, rather than watching TED (Technology, Entertainment, Design) talk shows or Celebrity speeches to understand how they keep engaged with the audiences.

6. **Google Drive:** Google Drive is an application (Jonathan M, 2019) for storing and sharing the files where the files can be assessed from any device. It is done using the virtual cloud which stores the file being uploaded via the Google account. In case of loss of power or accidental crashes in the computer while working will destroy the entire data created which can be overcome by using this which automatically saves the document in the cloud. It is very much useful in submitting assignments to the teachers where the file can be made only viewable by the teacher. Also, teachers will review the assignments and add remarks directly to the document rather than reviewing the bundles of papers.
7. **Zoom:** Zoom is a cloud-based video conferencing service providing application (Maggie T, 2022), through which users can make online meetings with the people. It has an added advantage of recording options through which users can record live meetings for future references. Various online conferences and training programs are conducted through a zoom meeting. People can join the meeting using the meeting link and password either on the phones or desktops. Online classes for students can also be conducted using this application. About 1000 participants and 49 on-screen videos can be performed providing a global video session.
8. **Socrative:** Socrative is an online assessment tool. It has two distinct features. One is the provision for creating a pre-prepared quiz for the students and secondly you can also conduct live question and answer sessions. In the case of a pre-prepared quiz, assessment can be done with multiple-choice, True/False, or one-word answers based on the choice of the creator. There is no limitation for adding questions and explanations can also be added if required. One of the interesting features is it will help the users to remember the skill, they are focussing by adding a common core curriculum tag to the assessments.
9. **Kahoot:** Kahoot is one of the most popular formative assessment tools (Jonathan W, 2021) for teachers as well as students who can create their own quizzes and question their classmates on a particular topic. There are many features provided like users can add points (hints) to each of the questions and the time limit for each question can also be fixed. The quickest fingers will be awarded more points. Similarly, images or video questions can also be added.
10. **MOOC'S:** Dave Cormier and Bryan Alexander coined the term MOOC (Waldrop M, 2013; Yuan L, 2013). MOOC's are one of the most revolutionary disruptive technology (Clayton MC, 1997). According to the IEEE CS 2022 Report, MOOCs are having the potential to alter the world by 2022 (Pretz K, 2014). The adaptability of MOOCs' are highly valued by students (Cripps AC, 2014). The students are very much interested in learning about a new subject to expand their

current knowledge and have desire to collect as many completion certificates as possible (Hew KF, 2014). They provide new ways of thinking and delivers courses in unconventional methods (Fox R, 2016). In 2012, Coursera, the first MOOC platform, was launched. Since then, other MOOC sites have emerged around the world. By the end of 2015, Coursera, edX, Udacity and FutureLearn (Sanchez-Gordon S) had 17 million, 5 million, 4 million and 3 million members respectively. The logo of various MOOC's is mentioned in Fig. 3.

Figure. 3 Logo of various MOOC's

a. Coursera

It is a for-profit enterprise developed by Stanford University professors Andrew Ng and Daphne Koller. It contains around 100 partners and 500 courses (Ibaraki S, 2014; Andrew Ng, 2014; About Coursera). It is a social entrepreneurship business that collaborates with many prominent universities across the world to offer free online courses to everyone (Shafiq H, 2017; Silvia A, 2015). In order to differentiate the platform from other types of MOOCs, the Coursera team searched for sound pedagogy on successful learning methods and then converted the concepts into procedures that could be implemented into the site's design. Some of the educational concepts that have helped students to learn more effectively includes the efficacy of online learning (Barbara M, 2010); the relevance of retrieval and testing for learning (Jeffrey DK, 2008); mastery learning (Benjamin SB, 1984); peer evaluations (Ralph R, 2001); and active learning in the classroom (Louis D, 2011). Many students have got jobs or promotions as a direct result of having these courses on their resumes (Chris G, 2012) as per the founder of Coursera.

b. EdX

It was founded by Harvard University and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, which is a non-profit organisation and open-source software platform (Rothberg MV, 2014; Schools and Partners). Various universities like Harvard, MIT, UC Berkeley, Microsoft, IBM and The Smithsonian provide free seminars to the students. It also offers numerous programmes (Blagojević M, 2015; Cobos R, 2017; Ch SK, 2013; Manganin N, 2014) like

- Workforce-relevant professional credentials
- Full online master's degree programmes
- Micro Bachelors
- Micro Masters etc.,
- Some of the micro credentials offered by Edx (Mara L, 2021; Dhawal S, 2021) are:

- **Micro Masters:** If the learner who obtained the certificate is accepted into the on-campus programme, the Micro Masters programme will give credit toward a Master's degree.
- **XSeries:** The XSeries is a collection of courses that will help you master a specific subject.
- **Professional Education:** Professional Education is a type of paid education that is aimed for people who are currently working in the area.
- **Professional Certificate:** Professional Certificates are equivalent to the Micro Masters and Xseries certificates. They do not provide a path to credit, unlike Micro Masters. They are said to be more employer-friendly than the Xseries.

c. **Udacity**

It places a greater emphasis on work training when compared to other MOOC's. Nanodegree is a micro-credential offered by Udacity (Wulf J, 2014; Lohr S, 2020). Some of the Nanodegree courses are made available for free to enrol. Generally, nanodegrees are aimed at in-demand talents in the realm of technology. They include video classes and human graded projects. Some of the nanodegrees course partners includes tech giants like Georgia Tech, Google etc., Like edX Micro Masters and Coursera Master Tracks Udacity Nanodegrees (Julia P, 2021) are online certificate programmes that can last anywhere between 3-6 months. They are designed to fit your schedule allowing you to learn at your own pace.

The participants receive various advantages on enrolling nanodegrees such as assistance with optimising resumes, LinkedIn profiles, and GitHub portfolios. Udacity has an active inventory of about 200 online courses and is the world's fourth most popular MOOC provider in terms of student enrollment (Dhawal S, 2021) (over 11.5 million learners).

d. **FutureLearn**

The Open University, which is a pioneer in distance learning and online education, established FutureLearn (Rizvi S, 2020; Shlenskaya N, 2019) in 2013. It currently has 175 partners, including many prestigious UK universities and Amnesty International and UNESCO as non-university partners. It has an active catalogue of about 1100 online courses and is the world's fifth most popular MOOC provider in terms of student enrolment (Pat B, 2021) (over 15 million learners).

Drawbacks

Some of the drawbacks in 20th century education includes:

- The Eye-to-Eye contact between student and teacher could be lost while taking notes in the classroom.
- The content displayed on the chalkboard cannot be stored and retrieved.

Some of the drawbacks in 21st century education includes:

- Because of the availability of many e-resources make the students very much confused between the reliable and unreliable resource.

- The technologies playing a major role in the student's daily activities could result in dependencies for information recall.
- Increased technology usage could disconnect students completely from the classroom.
- Students may get distracted in such a way they are more interested in the rewards; they receive through the applications rather than understanding the concepts they learn.
- Prolonged usage of various technologies could also affect the physical and mental health of the students.

Conclusion

The evolution of various technologies in the field of education has paved the way for providing new experiences to the students as well as teachers. Many of these tools can be utilized by the teachers to motivate the students who might usually disconnect from the class. But at the same time, rapid exploitation and misuse of these e-resources should be controlled by the teachers and parents by enforcing healthy boundaries to get the best results from the students. Technology in every sector has opened the doors for many opportunities, likewise, technology in the classrooms has taken teaching to the next level providing wider opportunities. Thus, with the help of all these education technologies it will be possible for the teachers to enhance their teaching methods by making the existing content more interesting and newer/ up to date contents can be created that were previously out of their reach due to various restrictions in the technologies.

Acknowledgments

Nil

Abbreviations

FDP - Faculty Development Program

OHP - Over Head Projector

TEL - Technology-enhanced learning

u-learning - Ubiquitous learning

M-learning - Mobile learning

MS-PowerPoint - Microsoft PowerPoint

MS-Word - Microsoft Word

MS-Excel - Microsoft Excel

E-learning - Electronic learning

PDF - Portable Document Format

PPT - PowerPoint Presentation

E-Commerce - Electronic Commerce

ICT - Information and Communications Technology

RSS - Real Simple Syndication

URL - Uniform Resource Locator

TED (Conference) - Technology, Entertainment, Design

MOOC – Massive Open Online Course

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